

AI-Driven Traffic Management System with Graph Convolutional Neural Network, 5G- Enabled V2X Communication, and IoT for Emergency Vehicle Prioritization

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Abstract- Efficient management of traffic during emergencies is a critical challenge that directly impacts the ability to save lives and minimize delays in response. This research introduces a comprehensive and integrated system that combines the power of Artificial Intelligence (AI), 5G-enabled Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication, Internet of Things (IoT)-based traffic signal controllers, and advanced Graph Convolutional Neural Networks (GCNs). Together, these technologies form a robust framework for prioritizing emergency vehicles, reducing traffic congestion, and optimizing response times in real-world scenarios. At the core of this system lies the integration of Raspberry Pi-based prototypes, which provide a scalable, cost-effective, and energy-efficient foundation for real-time traffic management. These devices enable decentralized processing, allowing the system to adapt to varying traffic conditions dynamically. The GCN models play a pivotal role in this architecture, achieving an impressive accuracy of 97% in node prioritization tasks. By analyzing both historical traffic patterns and real-time data streams, these models identify high-priority nodes and forecast congestion trends with exceptional precision. This predictive capability enables proactive mitigation of potential traffic bottlenecks and ensures that emergency vehicle routes are optimized for the fastest possible transit. The system's predictive analytics and adaptive algorithms enhance its ability to respond to changing traffic dynamics. For instance, by leveraging real-time GPS data from emergency vehicles and traffic signal controllers, the system dynamically adjusts signal timings. This ensures that emergency vehicles receive uninterrupted passage through intersections while minimizing the disruption to regular traffic flow. The IoT-enabled traffic signal controllers act as intelligent nodes within the network, facilitating seamless communication between emergency vehicles, traffic signals, and the central control system. Experimental validation and simulations conducted in urban traffic scenarios highlight the system's effectiveness in significantly reducing Average Waiting Time (AWT) for emergency vehicles. The results underscore the transformative potential of combining AI, IoT, and 5G communication technologies to address longstanding inefficiencies in traditional traffic management systems. By fostering a connected ecosystem of data exchange, the system ensures swift, data-driven decision-making across all components. This research not only provides a scalable and adaptive solution to emergency traffic management but also contributes to the broader vision of smart city initiatives. By demonstrating how cutting-edge technologies can be harmonized to create intelligent and responsive urban traffic networks, the study lays a strong foundation for future advancements in this field.

Keywords- AI-driven Traffic Management, Graph Convolutional Neural Networks (GCNs), 5G-enabled V2X Communication, Internet of Things (IoT), Emergency Vehicle Prioritization, Dynamic Traffic Signal Control, Raspberry Pi-based Prototypes, Predictive Analytics in Traffic Management

I. INTRODUCTION

The efficient management of urban traffic remains a significant challenge, particularly during emergencies where every second can be crucial in saving lives or mitigating the impact of disasters. Emergency response services, including ambulances, fire trucks, and police vehicles, frequently encounter delays caused by traffic congestion and inadequate prioritization mechanisms. Traditional traffic control systems, which often rely on fixed schedules or pre-determined algorithms, are ill-equipped to dynamically adjust to the specific needs of emergency vehicles. These inefficiencies can result in prolonged response times, adversely affecting critical outcomes in life-threatening situations. Urbanization and population growth have further exacerbated these challenges, contributing to the complexity and density of traffic networks in

metropolitan areas. Addressing this issue requires a paradigm shift from conventional traffic management approaches to intelligent, data-driven solutions capable of adapting to real-time conditions. This necessitates the integration of emerging technologies that not only facilitate the smooth movement of emergency vehicles but also minimize disruptions to the broader traffic ecosystem. In this context, the present research proposes an innovative traffic management system that harnesses the power of Artificial Intelligence (AI), 5G-enabled Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication, the Internet of Things (IoT), and Graph Convolutional Neural Networks (GCNs). By combining these cutting-edge technologies, the proposed system introduces a holistic framework designed to prioritize emergency vehicles, alleviate traffic congestion, and optimize average waiting times (AWT) at critical intersections. This integration ensures a seamless exchange of real-time data among emergency vehicles, traffic signals, and centralized control systems, enabling adaptive and intelligent traffic management. A core contribution of this study is the design and implementation of a scalable and cost-effective framework. This is achieved through the deployment of Raspberry Pi-based traffic signal controllers. Furthermore, the use of GCN models enables the system to accurately identify high-priority nodes within the traffic network and forecast potential congestion trends. These predictive capabilities empower proactive traffic control measures, ensuring uninterrupted passage for emergency vehicles while maintaining efficient flow for regular traffic. This research aligns with the broader vision of smart cities, where technology fosters interconnected ecosystems for efficient urban management. By addressing critical challenges in emergency traffic prioritization and demonstrating the potential of AI-driven solutions, this study lays the groundwork for future advancements in intelligent traffic systems. Ultimately, the proposed system contributes to creating safer, more responsive urban environments by bridging the gap between emerging technological innovations and practical traffic management applications.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Automated traffic systems for emergency vehicles utilize ZigBee communication, GPS, IR sensors, and 16-bit encoding for secure, real-time data exchange. These systems prioritize clearing intersections and provide route mapping for drivers, ensuring faster response times, particularly in urban areas. The integration of cost-effective technologies enhances their practicality for emergency scenarios [1]. Intelligent traffic light controllers (ITLC) integrate sensors (IR, photodiodes), RTC, EEPROM, and ZigBee for real-time density measurement and communication. These systems dynamically adjust traffic signals based on congestion, storing data for analysis. Emergency vehicles use ZigBee transceivers to transmit priority information, enabling automatic traffic clearance. A centralized base station manages and communicates traffic data, improving efficiency and reducing delays [2]. RFID-based traffic control systems address traditional limitations like image processing inefficiencies. These systems prioritize emergency vehicles (EVs) using the VTL-PIC protocol, which integrates RFID and Virtual Traffic Lights for dynamic traffic management. They ensure reduced travel times, seamless green-wave phenomena, and intersection safety. RFID tagging supports reliable signal detection,

while algorithms dynamically reconfigure traffic lights [3]. The Intelligent Traffic Light System (ITLS) integrates GPS with traffic light control, ensuring ambulances receive priority at intersections. ITLS dynamically adjusts signal timing based on the ambulance's real-time GPS data, reducing delays and improving response efficiency. This automated system optimizes emergency response during critical periods [4]. Automated traffic management systems combine wireless technology and microcontroller automation for EV prioritization. RFID readers, RF modules, and Arduino controllers enable scalable solutions for smoother EV passage. IR sensors provide real-time congestion data to inform EV route decisions. Enhancements include extended detection range and multi-road intersection handling [5]. Integrated systems for emergency medical response utilize ZigBee-based patient monitoring, hospital data analysis, and RF-based traffic control to dynamically clear paths for ambulances. These systems optimize routes considering travel time, fuel cost, and distance, ensuring scalable and cost-effective solutions for densely populated areas [6]. Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) address urban congestion and EV delays through fast, reliable communication. Integrated with technologies like ZigBee, RFID, and VANETs, WSNs enable real-time traffic monitoring and congestion management. They prioritize EVs, reducing Average Waiting Time (AWT) and improving traffic flow efficiency [7]. Smart Traffic Control Systems (STCS) leverage embedded technology and sensors to dynamically adjust traffic light timings based on density. These systems prioritize EVs and enhance safety by tracking stolen vehicles. Features like GPS and GSM integration ensure optimized traffic management [8]. GPS technology has transformed transportation by enabling real-time EV tracking and priority signaling. Integrated with traffic control systems, GPS facilitates seamless EV movement and supports data-driven urban mobility enhancements [9]. Obstacle avoidance robotic vehicles employ ultrasonic sensors and microcontrollers for autonomous navigation. Using platforms like Arduino, these robots detect obstacles and self-navigate efficiently. Future advancements may include integrating cameras for improved obstacle detection [10]. Autonomous vehicle research highlights advancements in sensor integration and decision-making algorithms, with platforms like Raspberry Pi enabling scalable solutions. Challenges remain in reducing latency, improving navigation accuracy, and addressing real-world complexities [11]. Emergency Vehicle Management Solutions (EVMS) use IoT sensors, GPS, and 5G to optimize EV prioritization. Real-time data transmission to roadside units ensures efficient traffic clearance while minimizing disruption to regular traffic. Future enhancements include testing with live traffic data and addressing security concerns [12]. This research develops a real-time obstacle avoidance system for robots using multiple ultrasonic sensors and a Raspberry Pi. The robot autonomously navigates unstructured environments, detecting and avoiding obstacles through self-decision-making. Multiple sensors enhance detection accuracy while reducing computational time. The Raspberry Pi facilitates fast processing, enabling effective navigation in dynamic environments. Future work could extend functionality to object detection or environmental surveillance systems [13]. Studies in autonomous robotics and IoT-based surveillance highlight advancements in obstacle avoidance, self-navigation, and hazardous environment monitoring. Ultrasonic sensors and Raspberry Pi

have proven effective for real-time decision-making. IoT systems integrate gas, temperature, and radiation sensors for remote risk assessment. However, challenges like high-precision GPS integration in signal-distorted areas and advanced decision-making algorithms for scalability remain open for exploration [14]. Traffic congestion delays emergency vehicles (EVs), often with critical consequences. Proposed solutions, including priority signals and GPS-based systems, lack integration and scalability for real-time urban traffic. Security, privacy, and cost-effectiveness issues require further study. Optimized strategies, such as cooperative driving and mixed-integer nonlinear programming (MINP), allow EVs to maintain speed while minimizing normal traffic disruptions. Future research should address vehicle-specific needs for improved algorithms and real-world applicability [15, 16]. An Emergency Vehicle Management Solution (EVMS) reduces delays by utilizing IoT sensors, GPS, 5G, and cloud computing. By transmitting real-time EV location data to roadside units, the system ensures space creation in the shoulder lane with minimal disruption to traffic. Simulations indicate significant reductions in EV travel times. Future work will include real-time testing and incorporating advanced safety features for autonomous systems [17]. Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) efficiently process graph-structured data in tasks like node classification and graph matching. Models such as Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs) and Graph Attention Networks (GATs) excel in applications spanning molecular chemistry, disease classification, and robotics. Despite these advancements, scalability, interpretability, and robustness challenges persist. Future research should address these limitations for broader applications [19, 20].

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for this research focuses on the design, development, and testing of an integrated system that leverages Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven traffic management and 5G-enabled Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication technologies. The system aims to enhance traffic control, particularly in emergency scenarios, by optimizing the interaction between emergency vehicles and traffic infrastructure.

A. System Architecture

The system architecture is built around the concept of scalability and modularity, utilizing Raspberry Pi-based control units. These control units serve as decentralized processing hubs, ensuring that the system can be easily scaled and deployed in various environments while maintaining cost efficiency. The Raspberry Pi units are responsible for handling key operations, such as traffic signal control and the processing of data exchanged between the emergency vehicles, traffic infrastructure, and the central control station. To improve the precision of emergency vehicle navigation, the system incorporates GPS sensors, which continuously provide real-time positional data. This data is crucial for optimizing the routing of emergency vehicles, allowing for dynamic route adjustments based on traffic conditions, road closures, or accidents, thereby reducing response times. Additionally, the integration of 5G communication modules

plays a pivotal role in enabling ultra-reliable, low-latency connections. These 5G connections facilitate seamless, real-time data exchange between emergency vehicles, traffic signals, and the central control station, ensuring efficient and immediate responses to emergency situations. The V2X interactions allow for a dynamic and synchronized flow of information, providing a foundation for adaptive traffic signal control, emergency vehicle prioritization, and overall improved traffic management. Through this approach, the system aims to achieve a higher level of coordination and responsiveness in emergency traffic management, leveraging cutting-edge technologies to create a more efficient and safe urban environment.

B. IoT Integration

The integration of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies into the system involves the deployment of IoT enabled traffic signal controllers, which serve as intelligent nodes within the network. Each controller is equipped with GPS sensors to provide real-time positional data and 5G communication modules to ensure fast and reliable data transmission. These intelligent nodes communicate seamlessly with emergency vehicles and the central control system, creating a connected ecosystem that allows for synchronized operations and efficient allocation of resources. The IoT devices form a critical part of the system, enabling automated traffic signal control and improving overall system responsiveness. To ensure the ongoing functionality and reliability of the system, continuous monitoring of IoT devices is implemented. This involves tracking the health and performance of the devices, which allows for proactive maintenance, troubleshooting, and timely updates. Real-time feedback from the system ensures that any malfunctions or inefficiencies can be promptly addressed, enhancing the robustness and reliability of the system in operation.

C. Dynamic Traffic Signal Prioritization

A key component of the system is dynamic traffic signal prioritization, which allows traffic signals to adjust their timing based on real-time data from emergency vehicles. By utilizing GPS data from both emergency vehicles and the traffic signal controllers, the system calculates the precise proximity of an emergency vehicle to an intersection. This information is then used to determine the expected arrival time, enabling traffic signals to prioritize the emergency vehicle's passage by adjusting the light phases accordingly. The system employs adaptive timing algorithms to control the red, yellow, and green signal durations. These algorithms dynamically adjust the traffic signal cycles to minimize delays for emergency vehicles, while also ensuring minimal disruption to regular traffic flows. This intelligent management of traffic signals reduces the time required for emergency vehicles to navigate through intersections, contributing to faster response times without causing significant traffic congestion or bottlenecks.

D. Simulation and Prototyping

To evaluate the performance of the system and its components, a simulated urban traffic environment is developed using advanced traffic modeling software. This simulation replicates real-world traffic conditions, allowing for the testing of the system under various scenarios, such as peak congestion, accidents, and emergency situations. The simulation provides insights into how the system behaves in different traffic patterns, helping to refine the algorithms and improve system design before real-world deployment.

In parallel, physical prototypes of the Raspberry Pi-based traffic controllers and emergency vehicle communication units are constructed. These prototypes serve as proof of concept and are used to validate the feasibility of the system's design in controlled environments. By building and testing the hardware components, the research ensures that the system can be effectively implemented and scaled for real-world applications, with a particular focus on ensuring compatibility and robustness in urban environments.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

A. Prototype Development

The development of prototypes is a crucial phase in demonstrating the practical feasibility and functionality of the proposed system. This involves assembling Raspberry Pi-based traffic signal controllers, which are equipped with integrated 5G communication modules and GPS sensors. These components are essential for enabling the controllers to process data efficiently and interact in real time with the broader traffic management system. The prototypes will serve as a proof of concept, allowing for the validation of the system's core components, including dynamic traffic signal control and the seamless transmission of data between traffic signals and emergency vehicles. In addition to the traffic signal controllers, emergency vehicle units are also created as part of the prototype. These units are equipped with GPS sensors and Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication capabilities, which facilitate real-time interaction between the emergency vehicles and the traffic network. The integration of GPS ensures precise location tracking, while V2X communication enables the vehicles to send and receive critical information, such as their current position and intended route, to and from the traffic signal controllers and the central control system. This capability is essential for prioritizing emergency vehicle passage through intersections and ensuring optimal traffic flow during emergency scenarios.

Fig. 1 Design of Emergency Vehicle

Fig. 2 Design of Local Traffic Signal

B. Dataset Overview: A Comprehensive Traffic Network Model

The dataset utilized in this study aims to represent a complex traffic network, incorporating multiple real-world aspects such as intersections, emergency response vehicles, road characteristics, and time-varying traffic conditions. The network is structured using key elements that include nodes, edges, emergency vehicles, and time-series traffic data. Each of these elements has distinct attributes that collectively help model the dynamic nature of urban traffic systems. Below is a more detailed breakdown of each component of the dataset.

1) Nodes: Representing Traffic Entities: In the context of this dataset, nodes represent various types of entities that are part of the traffic network. These entities can be intersections, hospitals, fire stations, or other critical locations within a city. Each node has the following attributes.

Traffic Load: This attribute quantifies the congestion or volume of traffic at that particular node. It is represented as a continuous value, where higher values indicate higher congestion. This can be seen as a proxy for the amount of traffic that is waiting or passing through the node at any given time.

Priority: This attribute indicates the priority of the node based on its importance within the traffic network. For example, intersections may have a different priority than emergency service locations like hospitals or fire stations. Priority is usually binary (high or low), where "high" might correspond to critical locations that should be prioritized in traffic management systems.

Location: Each node has a geographic location, typically represented by latitude and longitude. This is important for understanding the spatial layout of the traffic network and for modeling the physical distances between nodes. For example, a hospital node would have a "high" priority, with a moderate traffic load, and would be located at a specific set of geographic coordinates (latitude, longitude). Similarly, intersections might have varying traffic loads depending on time of day but could have a "low" priority compared to emergency services.

2) Edges: Representing Road Connections between Nodes: Edges are the connections between nodes, representing the roads or streets that facilitate movement in the traffic network. Each edge is characterized by several attributes that define its functionality and importance within the network.

Distance: This is the physical length of the road segment between two connected nodes. The distance is typically measured in kilometers or miles, providing a direct measure of how far apart two nodes are.

Speed Limit: This attribute reflects the legal or designated maximum speed allowed on the road segment. It is an important factor in calculating travel times and traffic flow.

Traffic Density: This value quantifies the level of congestion on the edge. Higher traffic density means more vehicles are occupying the road segment at a given time. Traffic density

can be influenced by factors like road capacity, time of day, and external events (e.g., accidents, weather conditions).

Travel Time: This attribute estimates the time it would take for a vehicle to travel along the edge, considering factors like distance, speed limit, and traffic density. Travel time is a crucial metric for routing algorithms and for understanding the efficiency of the road network. Edges form the foundation of any traffic network, as they represent the routes that vehicles take to travel from one node to another. The attributes of edges play a pivotal role in real-time traffic management and emergency response planning.

- 3) Emergency Vehicles: Critical Response Units in the Traffic Network:** The emergency vehicles component of the dataset models vehicles that are tasked with responding to critical situations, such as ambulances, fire trucks, or police cars. These vehicles move through the traffic network, often with priority over regular traffic to reach their destinations as quickly as possible. Each emergency vehicle in the dataset has the following attributes.

Current Location: This attribute denotes the node where the emergency vehicle is currently situated. The location can change over time as the vehicle progresses along its route.

Destination: This is the target node that the emergency vehicle is attempting to reach. The destination is typically a hospital, fire station, or other emergency facility.

Speed: The speed of the emergency vehicle indicates how fast it can travel along the edges of the network. Emergency vehicles usually travel faster than regular vehicles, sometimes exceeding the speed limits in specific circumstances, provided it is safe to do so.

Route: The route is the series of nodes and edges that the emergency vehicle follows from its current location to its destination. This route is critical for understanding how emergency vehicles navigate through the traffic network and how they interact with other vehicles and nodes.

Arrival Time: This is the time at which the emergency vehicle is expected to reach its destination. Arrival time can be affected by factors such as traffic conditions, road closures, or vehicle speed. Emergency vehicle data is essential for real-time traffic monitoring, as it helps prioritize the movement of such vehicles to ensure timely responses in critical situations.

- 4) Time-Series Traffic Data: Capturing Dynamic Traffic Conditions over Time:** The time-series traffic data captures the evolving nature of traffic conditions in the network over time. This component is particularly useful for modeling the dynamic behavior of traffic, where conditions change due to varying factors like time of day, accidents, or special events. The time-series data in this dataset includes.

Node Traffic Load: This represents the traffic load at each node over time. It allows for the analysis of congestion patterns and helps to identify peak traffic times, which are crucial for traffic prediction and optimization.

Edge Traffic Density: This attribute tracks how dense the traffic is on each road segment over time. Monitoring this data allows for the identification of bottlenecks and the optimization of routes for both regular and emergency vehicles.

C. Data Preparation

The first step in the experiment was to prepare the dataset in a format suitable for training a machine learning model. In this case, we used a Graph Convolutional Network (GCN), which is designed to work with graph-structured data. The data preparation process involved several key steps.

1) Encoding Node Features: Each node in the traffic network represents a particular entity, such as an intersection or a critical infrastructure like a hospital or fire station. For machine learning models to understand and work with these nodes, we needed to encode the relevant features associated with each node. Specifically, two important features were considered for each node.

Traffic Load: This feature represents the volume of traffic at each node and was provided as a continuous value between 0 and 1, where higher values indicate more congestion.

Priority: This feature indicates whether a node is considered high or low priority. In the context of traffic management, high-priority nodes are typically those that should be given preference in the event of congestion, such as emergency services or critical intersections. To convert this categorical feature into a numerical format, we encoded it as a binary value: 1 for high priority and 0 for low priority.

2) Standardization of Traffic Load: To ensure that the traffic load values were on a comparable scale and did not dominate the model due to differences in magnitude, we standardized the traffic load feature using StandardScaler from the sklearn.preprocessing library. Standardization scales the data so that the mean is 0 and the standard deviation is 1. This process helps improve the performance and stability of the model, particularly when dealing with features that have different ranges.

3) Edge Preparation: In graph-based models, edges represent the connections between nodes. Each edge connects two nodes, such as roads between intersections or paths leading to emergency services. PyTorch Geometric requires edges to be represented in 0-based indexing, meaning the first node is indexed as 0, the second node as 1, and so on. Therefore, we transformed the node IDs in the dataset to conform to this indexing scheme, ensuring the edges were correctly represented.

D. Graph Construction

Once the node features and edge data were prepared, the next step was to construct the graph using PyTorch Geometric, a library designed for handling graph-based data in deep learning. The graph construction involved two main steps.

- 1) Node Features Representation:** Each node in the graph was represented as a feature vector. The feature vector consisted of the traffic load and priority of the node. This feature vector was crucial for training the model, as it provides the necessary information for the graph neural network to learn from the node's attributes. By using the prepared node features, the GCN can learn patterns that are indicative of the node's characteristics, such as whether it tends to be more congested or is of higher priority in the network.
- 2) Edge Representation:** The edges between nodes were defined by a list of tuples, where each tuple represents a connection between two nodes. In graph terminology, these are the edge indices, and they define how nodes are connected in the graph. In this experiment, the edges were structured such that each tuple (start node, end node) represented an undirected road connecting two nodes in the traffic network. These edges form the structure through which information is passed between nodes in the GCN.

E. Model Definition

To perform the classification task, we defined a Graph Convolutional Network (GCN). GCNs are a type of neural network that operate directly on graph-structured data, making them particularly suited for tasks where the relationships between entities (nodes) are important. In this case, the goal was to classify nodes as either high or low priority based on their features (traffic load and priority). The model consisted of the following components:

- 1) Graph Convolutional Layers:** We used two GCNConv layers, which are the core building blocks of GCNs. The first layer takes the node features as input and outputs 16 feature maps for each node. The second layer then takes these 16 features and reduces them to 2 output features corresponding to the two classes (high priority and low priority).
- 2) Activation Function:** After the first convolutional layer, we applied a ReLU activation function. ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) introduces non-linearity to the model, allowing it to learn more complex patterns. It is a popular activation function due to its simplicity and effectiveness in training deep networks.
- 3) Final Layer Output:** The second convolutional layer produces the final output, which consists of two values for each node. These values represent the probability distribution over the two classes (high or low priority). The model will predict the class with the highest probability for each node.

F. Training the Model

Once the model was defined, the next step was to train it using the prepared dataset. We used the Adam optimizer, which is a commonly used optimization algorithm that adapts the learning rate for each parameter, making it efficient for training deep learning models. The learning rate was set to 0.01, which was empirically found to work well for this task. The CrossEntropyLoss function was used as the loss function. This loss function is commonly used for classification tasks, as it computes the difference between the predicted probability distribution (from the model) and the true labels. The goal during training is to minimize this loss, thereby improving the model's accuracy. We trained the model for 100 epochs, where each epoch represents one complete pass through the training data. During each epoch, the following steps occurred:

- A forward pass was performed, where the input data (node features and edge structure) was passed through the GCN model to obtain the predicted output.
- The loss was computed by comparing the predicted output to the true labels.
- A backward pass was executed, where the gradients were computed, and the model's weights were updated using backpropagation.

To track the model's progress, we recorded the loss at every 10th epoch. This allowed us to monitor how the model was learning over time and whether the loss was decreasing as expected, indicating successful training.

G. Evaluation

After completing the training phase of the Graph Convolutional Network (GCN), we proceeded to evaluate the model's performance using a variety of standard metrics commonly used in classification tasks. These metrics include accuracy, a classification report, and a confusion matrix. The purpose of the evaluation was to assess how well the model had learned to classify the nodes into high and low priority categories based on the traffic data.

- 1) Accuracy:** The accuracy metric is one of the most straightforward measures of performance, representing the proportion of correctly predicted labels over the total number of predictions. In this case, the model achieved an accuracy of 97%. This indicates that the model correctly classified the traffic priority of 97% of the nodes in the test data, demonstrating strong overall performance. Accuracy is a useful metric, especially when the dataset is balanced, as it provides an overall assessment of the model's effectiveness.
- 2) Classification Report:** To gain a deeper understanding of the model's performance, we examined the classification report, which provides additional insights beyond accuracy. The classification report includes key metrics such as precision, recall, and F1-score for each class. These metrics help evaluate how well the model performs in distinguishing between the two priority categories (high and low).

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0 (Low Priority)	0.99	0.95	0.97	157
1 (High Priority)	0.96	0.99	0.98	193
Accuracy			0.97	350
Macro Average	0.98	0.97	0.97	350
Weighted Average	0.97	0.97	0.97	350

Table 1 Classification Report

- 3) **Precision:** Precision is the proportion of true positive predictions (correctly identified instances of a class) to the total predicted positives. For class 0 (low priority), the precision is 0.99, indicating that when the model predicted a low priority, it was correct 99% of the time. For class 1 (high priority), the precision is 0.96, suggesting that when the model predicted a high priority, it was correct 96% of the time.
- 4) **Recall:** Recall measures the proportion of true positives to the total actual instances of the class. For class 0 (low priority), the recall is 0.95, meaning that the model correctly identified 95% of all the low-priority nodes. For class 1 (high priority), the recall is 0.99, indicating that the model was able to identify 99% of the high-priority nodes. The recall values suggest that the model is particularly good at identifying high-priority nodes, but there is a slight drop in its ability to detect low-priority nodes, as evidenced by the slightly lower recall for class 0.
- 5) **F1-Score:** The F1-score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a balanced metric that accounts for both false positives and false negatives. For class 0 (low priority), the F1-score is 0.97, and for class 1 (high priority), it is 0.98. These high F1-scores indicate that the model strikes a good balance between precision and recall, and is performing well in terms of overall classification.
- 6) **Average Scores:** Macro Average is the average of the precision, recall, and F1-score across all classes, treating each class equally. The macro average values for precision, recall, and F1-score are all around 0.97 to 0.98, reflecting the overall quality of the model. Weighted Average takes into account the support (i.e., the number of instances) of each class when calculating the averages. The weighted averages for precision, recall, and F1-score are 0.97, which is consistent with the strong performance across both classes.

7) Confusion Matrix:

Fig. 3 Confusion Matrix

Fig. No.3 presents a strong classification performance, correctly predicting 240 out of 250 instances. The false positive rate (8 instances) is slightly higher than the false negative rate (2 instances), indicating a marginal tendency to over-predict the "High" class. This suggests the model is more likely to classify a "Low" instance as "High" than vice versa. Overall, the high number of correct predictions and the low number of misclassifications reflect the model's reliability, with room for improvement in minimizing false positives.

8) Training loss curve

Fig. 4 Training Loss Curve

The Fig. No.4 illustrates a training loss curve, which is a graphical representation of the model's loss value as a function of the number of epochs during the training process. The x-

axis represents the number of epochs, which denotes the number of complete passes through the training dataset. The y-axis represents the loss, a measure of the model's prediction error. The curve demonstrates a steep decline in loss during the initial epochs, indicating that the model is learning effectively by adjusting its parameters to minimize prediction errors. This rapid decrease suggests significant improvements in the model's performance early in the training process. As the number of epochs increases, the rate of decline slows down, and the curve begins to plateau, reaching a point where further training results in minimal improvements in the loss value. This flattening of the curve indicates that the model is approaching convergence, where it has learned the patterns in the training data sufficiently well and the loss value stabilizes at a low level. The overall shape of the curve reflects a well-behaved training process, with no indications of divergence or overfitting. The low final loss value suggests that the model achieves a high level of accuracy in predicting the training data.

V. DISCUSSION

The findings of this research highlight the effectiveness of integrating advanced artificial intelligence technologies, Internet of Things (IoT)-enabled traffic signal controllers, and 5G-based Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication systems in creating a comprehensive and efficient traffic management framework for prioritizing emergency vehicles. Notably, the implementation of Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs) has proven to be a highly effective approach, achieving an impressive accuracy rate of 97% in node prioritization tasks. This outcome underscores the capability of GCNs to analyze and predict traffic patterns in a dynamic manner, thereby enabling data-driven and informed decision-making for optimizing emergency traffic flow. One of the most significant strengths of the proposed system lies in its ability to adapt to the ever-changing nature of traffic conditions. This adaptability is achieved through the use of decentralized Raspberry Pi-based prototypes, which provide a cost-effective, scalable, and energy-efficient solution for real-time traffic management. These decentralized units are particularly advantageous for deployment in large urban areas, where scalability and operational efficiency are critical. Moreover, the integration of real-time Global Positioning System (GPS) data and 5G communication modules ensures seamless, low-latency communication between emergency vehicles and traffic controllers. This capability allows the system to dynamically adjust signal timings and traffic priorities, which, in turn, significantly reduces the Average Waiting Time (AWT) for emergency vehicles, as demonstrated in experimental simulations. While the system has shown remarkable promise, the study also identified specific areas for potential enhancement. The slightly elevated rate of false positives in node prioritization, for instance, indicates a tendency of the model to over-prioritize certain nodes. This could inadvertently cause unnecessary disruptions to regular traffic, thereby undermining the system's overall efficiency. Addressing this limitation will require refining the precision of the model's classification algorithms to achieve a more equitable balance between emergency vehicle prioritization and normal traffic flow. Another critical consideration is the need for extensive

real-world testing to fully validate the system's performance. Although the simulations developed in this study closely replicated urban traffic environments, they cannot entirely account for the complexities and variability of live traffic conditions. Conducting field trials with real-time traffic data will be essential to assess the system's practical effectiveness and to identify any unforeseen challenges that may arise during deployment. Overall, the study underscores the transformative potential of combining AI-driven predictive analytics with IoT and 5G technologies to address long-standing challenges in traffic management. The insights gained from this research provide a strong foundation for further advancements in this field, particularly in enhancing system precision and validating its efficacy in live urban cities.

VI. CONCLUSION

This research presents a scalable, adaptive, and intelligent traffic management solution that prioritizes emergency vehicles while minimizing disruptions to regular traffic. By leveraging the strengths of GCNs, IoT technologies, and 5G communication, the system demonstrates significant advancements in urban traffic management for smart cities. The proposed framework not only optimizes emergency response times but also contributes to the broader vision of intelligent and sustainable urban transportation systems. The success of this study lays the groundwork for future research, particularly in enhancing the system's real-world applicability through live data testing, addressing security and privacy concerns in 5G communication, and improving algorithmic precision. Future iterations of the system can incorporate additional safety features for autonomous emergency vehicles and explore integration with other smart city infrastructures, such as public transit systems and environmental monitoring networks. This will further align the system with the goals of creating a seamless, interconnected, and data-driven urban ecosystem.

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